

TABLE I—METAL CHELATES OF α -IODOACETOACETANILIDE

Complex	Solvent used for recrystallisation	Yield (%)	m. p. (°C)	Magnetic moment (B. M.)	Molecular Weight [†]	Molar Conductance $\text{ohm}^{-1}\text{cm}^2 \text{mole}^{-1}$	Analytical Data [†]		
							C (%)	H (%)	N (%)
BeL ₂	*	44	**	D			38.98 (39.15)	2.92 (2.94)	4.11 (4.57)
CuL ₂	*	50	130	1.73			35.25 (39.96)	2.32 (2.69)	3.81 (4.19)
CrL ₂	*	25	220 d	3.82			37.19 (37.59)	2.12 (2.82)	4.28 (4.38)
FeL ₂	Benzene-pet-ether	28	**	5.92	985 (962)	6.82	36.98 (37.44)	4.62 (2.80)	4.19 (4.36)

D—Diamagnetic

d-decomposes

* Insoluble

** Not melting or visibly decomposing upto 360°

[†] Calculated values in brackets.

Attempted synthesis of cobalt(III) chelate was unsuccessful, since aeration of the reaction mixture containing cobalt(II) and ligand, caused liberation of iodine.

Only the iron(III) complex could be recrystallised, and was found nonconducting in methanol. Its monomeric nature was revealed by its molecular weight, determined cryoscopically in benzene. Other complexes were first washed with water and then repeatedly with hot alcohol and acetone. Details of the complexes obtained analytically pure are brought out in Table 1. Infrared spectra of the complexes (Nujol mull) showed that, in conformity with the expected β -amidoenolate structure of the ligand moiety^{1,2}, the carbonyl bands are lowered to about 1565 and 1550 cm^{-1} , and the N-H stretching frequency raised to about 3300 cm^{-1} , in the metal chelates. As compared to the spectra of the corresponding metal chelates of (unsubstituted) acetoacetanilide, the upward shift of the N-H stretching band is less, probably because weak inter- or intramolecular hydrogen-bonding of N-H with the halogen, occurs also in the metal chelates.

A Toshniwal conductivity bridge, Gouy-type balance, Perkin-Elmer 137 infrared spectrometer and Varian A 60 D N.M.R. spectrometer were used for conductance, magnetic and spectral measurements.

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Complexation Reaction of Iron(III) with Salicyloylhydrazide

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THE complexation of salicyloylhydrazide with manganese¹, titanium² and vanadium³ has been reported in literature. This complexation is useful in the gravimetric determination of titanium in the industrial samples. The reddish brown coloured complex of salicyloylhydrazide with Fe(III) in 80% (v/v) aqueous ethanol has been studied and reported in the present communication.

Experimental

The salicyloylhydrazide was dissolved in absolute alcohol to get 0.02 M solution. The Fe(III) solution was prepared in double distilled water from ferric chloride (BDH 'AnalaR') and standardized to 0.1 M solution⁴. The absorbance was measured with Bausch and Lomb Spectronic 20-spectrophotometer in 80% (v/v) aqueous ethanol at pH 3.2 keeping the temperature at $35 \pm 1^\circ$. The pH was adjusted to 3.2 by adding sodium hydroxide or hydrochloric acid and it was measured with 'Systronics' pH-meter using glass and calomel electrodes.

Results and Discussion

In order to select the wavelength for the maximum absorbance by the complex 8×10^{-4} moles of Fe(III)

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ion and 4×10^{-3} moles of salicyloylhydrazide were taken in 25 ml of 80% (v/v) aqueous ethanol. The pH of the solution was maintained at 3.2 by using sodium hydroxide or hydrochloric acid. The absorbance was measured at different wavelengths against reagent blank prepared under identical conditions. The complex was found to have maximum absorbance at 490 nm.

To study the effect of time 4×10^{-3} moles of salicyloylhydrazide and 8×10^{-4} moles of Fe(III) ion were taken in 25.0 ml of 80% (v/v) aqueous ethanol at pH 3.2. The absorbance was measured after regular intervals of time. No change in the absorbance of the solution was observed in about 4 hrs but after this the absorbance decreased slowly.

A series of solutions containing 1 ml of 1×10^{-3} M metal and varying amounts of ligand were prepared. The volume was made 25.0 ml in 80% (v/v) aqueous ethanol at pH 3.2 in each case. The absorbance was measured against reagent blank at 490 nm. It was observed that the optical density becomes practically constant when about 25 times molar excess of ligand was present.

Composition of the complex :

The nature and composition of the complex was studied by method of Vosburgh and Cooper⁵, Job's method of continuous variation⁶, mole ratio method⁷ and slope ratio method⁸. All the results confirmed the metal to ligand ratio as 1:2 in the complex.

From the absorbance at various concentrations of Fe^{3+} per ml of the solution it was observed that Beer's law is obeyed upto 8 μg of Fe^{3+} per ml of solution.

Effect of the presence of other ions :

A large number of standard solutions containing anions and cations were prepared. The effect of these ions on the absorbance of the complex of Fe(III) with salicyloylhydrazide was studied. It was found that the addition of solutions containing Ag^+ , Sn^{2+} , Co^{2+} , VO^{2+} , Hg_2^{2+} , In^{3+} , ZrO^{2+} , CNS^- , $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ and AsO_4^{3-} interfered in the formation of the complex. The solution containing Be^{2+} , Na^+ , K^+ , NH_4^+ , Mg^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Sr^{2+} , Ba^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Hg^{2+} , Y^{3+} , La^{3+} , Ce^{3+} , Al^{3+} , Th^{4+} , UO_2^{2+} , CO_3^{2-} , CH_3COO^- , NO_3^- , F^- , Cl^- , Br^- , IO_3^- , $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$, SO_4^{2-} , WO_4^{2-} and tartarate ions did not interfere in the reaction.

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New Zinc(II) Complexes with the Schiff Bases Derived from Salicylaldehyde or Substituted Salicylaldehyde and Orthoaminobenzylalcohol

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THE structure of N-alkylsalicylaldimines embodies several key molecular features common to pyridoxal mediated reactions and N-alkylsalicylaldimines are chemical prototypes of pyridoxal and the B₆ vitamins. The study of coordination complexes of N-alkylsalicylaldimines is of biochemical and biophysical interest. We report in this note the synthesis and characterisation of new zinc(II) complexes with the Schiff bases (I) derived from salicylaldehyde, 5-bromosalicylaldehyde, 5-chlorosalicylaldehyde, 3, 5-dichlorosalicylaldehyde, 2-hydroxynaphthaldehyde and orthoaminobenzylalcohol. Although there has been considerable research interest

I.R = H, 5-chloro, 5-bromo, 5-nitro, 3,5-dichloro and 5,6-benzo.

on the coordination complexes of Schiff bases with common metal ions like Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Fe^{3+} etc., very little work has been done on the Schiff base complexes of zinc(II)^{1,2}.

Experimental

The metal content was determined by titrating with EDTA using Eriochrome Black-T as an indicator³ after igniting the complex to ZnO and converting it to ZnSO_4 . Carbon and hydrogen analyses were done by Ciba Geigy Research Centre, Bombay. The nitrogen analyses were done microanalytically. The conductance measurements were carried out in methanol with the